

MAPPING THE LUNAR SUBSURFACE WITH A FULL POLARIMETRIC GROUND PENETRATING RADAR: SIMULATIONS ON A VARIETY OF TERRAINS. L. Harrar¹, A. Le Gall¹, V. Ciarletti¹, E. Brighi^{1,2}, Y. Hervé³, N. Oudart¹, A. Reineix⁴, C. Guiffaut⁴, M. Gilles⁵, ¹LATMOS, UVSQ, Guyancourt, France (lucy.harrar@latmos.ipsl.fr, alice.legall@latmos.ipsl.fr, valerie.ciarletti@latmos.ipsl.fr), ²LGL-TPE, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Lyon, France, ³SCIENTEAMA, Hérouville-Saint-Clair, France, ⁴XLim, Limoges, France, ⁵IAP, Paris, France.

Introduction: The Lunar South Pole and the nature of its subsurface has been long debated by the scientific community. A strong focus has been given to the Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSR) of the Moon, which are suspected to uncover large quantities of water ice in their subsurface [4]. Mini-RF, onboard the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter, has mapped the polar regions of the Moon and its PSRs, using a polarimetric product called the Circular Polarization Ratio (CPR). It has revealed anomalously high CPR values in some craters and PSRs, and sparked a debate on their interpretation as a radar signature of water ice. So far, the few Ground Penetrating Radars (GPR), such as the LPR onboard the Chang’e-4 rover, that have investigated the lunar subsurface did not have polarimetric capabilities and therefore provide only limited support for the interpretation of the CPR. Fortunately, future lunar missions plan to embark polarimetric GPR such as the LGPR (see Le Gall et al., this conference), or the LPR on board Chang’e 7 rover while targeting the South polar region of the Moon. In this work, we present numerical simulations of polarimetric GPR measurements on a variety of terrains relevant to the lunar context and investigate how their associated CPR values vary both spatially and with frequency. Doing so, we identify new and complementary radar signatures of depolarizing phenomena.

Characterizing the Lunar PSRs using Circular Polarization Ratio: The PSRs are regions that remain, almost permanently, in the shadows. The low obliquity of the Moon with respect to the ecliptic plane, as well as the geomorphology of these regions, explain why the solar rays cannot reach them. For these reasons, most PSRs are located at the Lunar Poles. These regions have been identified by solar illumination models [1], and studied by a variety of instruments. Near-IR absorption features of water ice, combined with temperature and albedo measurements, were identified as direct evidence of the presence of surface water ice, at the lunar poles [4].

However, the SAR data, and in particular the polarimetric products of these regions, are hard to interpret as such. Mini-RF, which is a S-band (12.6 cm) SAR, mapped a large portion of the lunar South Pole with its derived polarimetric products, including the CPR (Fig. 1).

The CPR is the ratio of the same-sense and opposite-sense normalized radar backscattering coefficients. In other words, the CPR quantifies the portion of incident intensity that was transmitted in a given

circular polarization (e.g. right circular polarization), and that is received in the opposite sense of polarization (e.g. left circular polarization).

A region with high CPR would then indicate surface depolarization. However, different configurations can originate such depolarization: water ice can contain small inclusions of air that are responsible for scattering phenomena, but surface roughness and rocky boulders can also act as corner reflectors, and change the polarization of the incident signal [6].

Furthermore, these CPR maps do not inform us on the scattering phenomena occurring deeper, in the subsurface.

Figure 1: Mini-RF CPR map of the Lunar North Pole showing anomalous high CPR values from different craters [2]

Full-Polarimetric GPRs: To have access to the information from the subsurface, while keeping the information provided from the polarimetric products, an increasing number of Planetary Science missions plan a full-polarimetric GPR as part of their rover payload. This work focuses on the numerical simulation of the operation of a WISDOM-like (Water Ice and Subsurface Deposit Observation on Mars) GPR. WISDOM is the GPR on board the Rosalind Franklin rover payload for the ExoMars Mission. It is a step-frequency radar, that operates in the frequency domain, between 0.5 and 3 GHz. It can transmit and receive in 2 linear orthogonal polarizations: Horizontal and Vertical (also denoted 0 and 1), resulting in 4 polarimetric configurations: 00, 11, 01 and 10.

This work is also relevant for future polarimetric GPR, on board lunar exploration missions. In particular, the Lunar Ground Penetrating Radar (LGPR) is currently being developed: it will inherit from WISDOM, but will operate at lower frequencies.

FDTD Simulations: To simulate the CPR obtained with a full-polarimetric GPR, we use a Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method. The

FDTD method solves Maxwell's equations for each step in time and space and outputs the electromagnetic field, received for a given polarimetric configuration, for each frequency of WISDOM's bandwidth.

In this work, we will present simulations on a variety of terrains, relevant to the lunar environment, with geoelectric properties derived from the Chang'E 3 and Chang'e 4 landing sites [7], including:

- Icy media filled with spherical inclusions of air, with different filling density.
- Homogeneous and heterogeneous media, with both rough and smooth interfaces.

Figure 2: Examples of simulated media: ice filled with spherical inclusions of air (left), homogeneous 3-layered medium, with rough interfaces (right)

CPR Calculation: For each medium, we compute the simulations for all 4 polarimetric configurations. We then calculate the resulting CPR, using conversion formula from a quad-polarization, to a circular polarization [3]. For a given simulation, we can control the size of the window in depth (or time delay) and in number of soundings, for which we calculate the CPR on. This methodology allows us to:

- Compare the mean CPR resulting from the whole subsurface, for different media.
- Compute a subsurface map of the CPR, to access local depolarization information for any given medium.

The particularity of simulating the CPR from a wideband instrument such as WISDOM or the LGPR, is to have access to its evolution on the whole frequency band, and not a single value for the center frequency (contrary to orbital radars as Mini-RF).

Preliminary Results: Global evolution of the mean CPR: We first studied the evolution of the mean CPR (averaged on the frequency band) for icy media, filled with a certain density of spherical inclusions of air (Fig. 2, left picture). The CPR of such media increases, and reaches above unity values, as the filling density of the media increases. This is consistent with the increase of multiple reflections and scattering events, which can lead to depolarization. We observe that the CPR reaches saturation, for a filling density of around 50-60%, which are almost equivalent to a homogeneous medium.

CPR vs frequency: The evolution of CPR with respect to WISDOM's bandwidth tends to show an increase with frequencies, though with notable oscillations. Its oscillatory behavior could initiate from interferences and scattering phenomena from the spheres in the subsurface. As we widen or reduce the windowing in time, we accentuate or reduce these oscillations, which seems to corroborate this hypothesis.

Mapping the subsurface with CPR: By adjusting the window in time and number of soundings, we can obtain a map of CPR values for the subsurface. Each pixel corresponds to an averaged value of the CPR for the given time and sounding window, on the whole frequency bandwidth. These CPR maps are complementary to the RGB radargrams, which are false-color radargrams, where each color represents one polarimetric configuration: 00, 11 and 01/10 respectively in Red, Green and Blue, giving a qualitative information on the local state of polarization. First experiments show that CPR maps could help quantify the depolarization resulting from roughness and/or heterogeneities, also identified in the RGB radargrams.

Figure 3: CPR map (left picture) from a 3-layer heterogeneous medium, with rough interfaces and its RGB Radargram (right picture)

Conclusion: Polarimetric GPR operating from the surface offer the opportunity to new analyses of the CPR: spatially, with CPR subsurface maps, but also through its spectral evolution to eventually identify frequential signatures for different depolarizing phenomena. FDTD simulations also allow us to compare the CPR obtained by polarimetric GPR, to the one measured from orbit. Such comparative analysis of the CPR is of high interest for future Lunar South Pole missions, with polarimetric GPR such as the LGPR or the LPR on board Chang'e 7 rover.

References: [1] Mazarico E. et al. (2011) *Icarus*, 211, 1066-1081. [2] Spudis P.D. et al. (2013), *JGR*, 118, 2016-2029. [3] Raney R. K. (2007), *IEEE*, 45, 3397-3404. [4] Li S. et al. (2018), *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 115, 8907-8912. [5] Fa W. and Cai Y. (2013), *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118, 1582-1608. [6] Campbell B.A. (2012), *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117; [7] Lai, J. (2019), *Geophys. Res. Letters*; 46, 12783-12793